

CHALLENGES AND SOLUTIONS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE STATE POLICY FOR THE SUPPORT OF YOUNG WOMEN AND THE PROTECTION OF THEIR RIGHTS AND INTERESTS

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Annotation: This article discusses the benefits provided to young women in our society by the legislation adopted in our country and the existing problems in women, as well as ways to solve these problems.

Keywords: Women's Support Law, Conditions, Privileges, Rights and Freedoms.

Respect for women is an ancient value of the Uzbek people. The role of women in the lives of great commanders, statesmen and great dynasties has been invaluable in our history. Among the women who left an indelible mark on the history of the nations of Central Asia were Sitorabonu (mother of Abu Ali Ibn Sina), Gavharshodbegim (mother of Mirzo Ulugbek), Saraymulkhanim (wife of Amir Temur), Kutlunigorkhanim (grandmother of Babur Mirza), Gulbadanbegim (daughter of Babur), Wali Orifakhon (mother of Bahauddin Nakshband), Robia Balkhi, Kurbonjon Dodkho, Zebuniso, Nodirabegim, Anbar atin Uvaisi. A number of researches about their spiritual as well as moral world and their role in the social, political and military processes of that time have been done. We are also proud to mention such famous women as Zulfiyakhanim, Sora Eshontorayeva, Tamarakhonim, Mukarrama Turgunbaeva, Saodat Kobulova, Fozila Sulaymonova, Muzayyana Alaviya, Buritosh Shodiyeva, who introduced the voice of the Uzbek people to the world in the recent past. If we put it into the words of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A.Karimov, “.. there are many criteria in the world that reflect the prestige and cultural level of the state and society. But there is a criterion that clearly reflects the spiritual maturity of any nation and people, which is determined by the attitude of society to women. In this sense, it is exactly safe to say that a nation that honors, respects, and upholds women will gain a reputation as a nation that demonstrates and affirms its high culture and noble values.”

At all times, women had to defend their rights and freedoms. Even after given opportunities to study and pursue careers without any restrictions, social old-fashioned opponents are still confronted with people who openly say that women are only for the family. Some people accept this, some are against public opinion, and there are still others who turn a blind eye to such words. They are

used to it, but nobody knows when this will end. Obedience is a quality that is highly valued in Eastern countries, including ours. This often stops the development of the girl's personality and sometimes ruins their life.

It is worth noting the efforts being done in our country to create the necessary conditions for the role of women in socio-political and economic life, as well as to increase their activity and initiative in various fields and sectors, to ensure their legitimate rights and interests. We have achieved success in this area during the years of independence, and the regulatory framework is being strengthened. About a hundred of national and international legal acts aimed at protecting the rights and interests of women have been adopted in our country. The guarantee of their observance is the Constitution. Every year, special state programs are approved and consistent work is carried out to improve the living conditions and quality of women in our country. Last year, in February, the President signed a decree aimed at radically improving the support of women. Clear tasks were set to increase the socio-political role and activity of women, timely identification of women in difficult living conditions, implementation of practical measures for their employment, effective prevention of delinquency and crime among women and to improve their legal culture and strengthen their spiritual and moral values. It is safe to say that there are radical changes in the lives of our women today because of the implementation of this decision. According to this resolution, research is being conducted on the points mentioned, and the rights and interests of women are being protected and their problems are being solved. Coming to this day, women in need of social protection and people with disabilities have been provided with targeted assistance and preferential housing. In addition, various exhibitions and fairs are organized to attract them to entrepreneurship, and vacancies are offered depending on the situation of our women. Besides that, a number of women in the neighborhood are regularly involved in crime prevention activities. However, there are still many problems. The reason for this is the low level of legal literacy and awareness. The educational work carried out is not always effective. Often, some women are so intimidated by their spouses, relatives and parents that they do not even dare to defend their rights. Women often explain the traces of domestic violence by their sudden collapse. This is due to the fact that our women do not know their rights and there are some superstitious ideas in our society that women and men are not equal. In this context, the adoption of the Law "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men", which consists of the regulation of relations in the field of equal rights and

opportunities for women and men lays the groundwork for the prevention of violence in our society. The resolution reflects the concept and types of discrimination against women in gender equality, the powers of the authorities, participation in public administration, obtaining loans for employment and hiring, and measures to prevent such violations of gender equality in entrepreneurship. Equality between women and men is guaranteed by the basic laws of many democracies, including the Constitution of Uzbekistan, as well as a number of international instruments, agreements, conventions and declarations concerning human rights. These include the UN Charter (June 26, 1945), the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (December 10, 1948), the Covenants on Civil and Political Rights, and international covenants, including a number of international agreements constituting the international system of human rights protection adopted by the UN in 1966. They set out nearly 70 international standards that make up the common concept of human rights for men and women. In addition, a new mechanism has been developed to protect the rights and interests of women in our society and to find solutions to their existing problems, to protect them from oppression and violence. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Protection of Women from Oppression and Violence" was adopted. This law, which came into force on September 3, 2019, was developed in accordance with the Presidential Decree of March 7, 2019 "On measures to further strengthen the guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurship." The purpose of this law is to protect women from all forms of oppression and violence in marriage, workplaces, educational institutions and elsewhere. Regulation of relations in this area, as well as ensuring legal and social protection of victims of oppression and violence are also important objectives of the law. The victim of harassment and violence now has the right to file a complaint with the relevant authorities and organizations or the court about the harassment or threat of harassment or violence. They also have the opportunity to receive free legal advice in special centers, through the hotline.

All of the above-mentioned laws provide a basis for women to have a place in our society and to be able to say their own voice. Ensuring that these laws are enforced and that women demand their rights will prevent them from being discriminated against and facing problems in our society. Meetings with women in the community to find solutions to the problems that are currently plaguing women can also help to prevent problems by organizing surveys among them. In addition, a special mechanism needs to be developed to further empower

women, including maternal and child health, entrepreneurship and other benefits for women. Pressure and violence against women have a negative psychological impact on their psyche. For this reason, improving the services of psychologists for women who have suffered from violence and oppression will help them stay spiritually healthy. The spiritual and physical health of women in society is a guarantee of a healthy generation in the future.

Having a baby in everyone's home brings joy and happiness to this family. There are sparks of hope and good wishes in the hearts of parents. As the child grows older, the dreams of the parents expand with him. When a child is born, parents must first pay attention to the child's upbringing and career. When a baby girl is born, she needs to be taught sewing, housekeeping, and child-rearing. This work should be taught not only by mothers but also by women in the whole neighborhood. After all, in our country it is called "seven neighborhood parents for one child." The role of the community and neighbors in the upbringing of children is invaluable. At this point, we can't help but remember another proverb: "Cock crows, As the Old/so does the young" . First of all, if the family and the neighborhood are peaceful and orderly, and if they are an example to others, then, of course, a child brought up in this environment will be disciplined. We all know that national traditions, values and customs play an important role in education. Of course, parents are responsible for passing them on to the next generation. This, like the problems, falls on the shoulders of not only the mother but also the father. The most important things a parent should teach their daughter are to be able to communicate properly and sweetly, to speak and listen when needed, to laugh and be upset, to express themselves and to develop . Unfortunately, there are also many parents who do not pay attention to their children at all. Others put pressure on them with excessive controls and restrictions, which may predispose to very serious consequences.

In our society, education and upbringing are never separated. They are inextricably linked. But we can't help but list some of the shortcomings and problems that our girls face in their education. First of all, let's talk about the dress code of our girls because as there is a saying "Clothes make the man", our girls are beautiful with Uzbek national dresses. However, some girls are falling into the vortex of "popular culture", imitating European countries. In my opinion, they are forgetting our national fabrics like adras and atlases. It is also heartbreaking that our girls are losing their culture of communication, talking and answering your questions rudely and rudely. Among our girls, there are some good qualities, such as respect for others, kindness and help to loved ones.

If you look around , you will see that some of them forget to help their elderly grandparents, to lighten their burdens, and even to greet them. The etiquette of walking the streets is also becoming an unaddressed memory for some of our girls. So what makes our girls reach this level? What mistakes are made in the education and upbringing of girls?

The child receives education from the family, the neighborhood, and education from educational institutions. At this point, a pertinent question arises: "Is there a gap between education and upbringing?" This gap can lead parents to say, "My child is learning from a teacher," considering themselves to the 2nd level in terms of educating, or to not pay enough attention to their child, and some teachers' words like "It is enough to finish my lesson" are resulting from their superficial view of students' interests and talents. Unfortunately, today there is a minority of parents who take into account the education of children, especially girls, and their interest and talent in the profession, and in turn support them. Neglect of their children, even the large number of parents who don't care and share their love with their offsprings and the lack of meaningful organization of girls' leisure time, as well as the fact that they are not engaged in any work, cause great changes in the lives of our girls and create negative qualities in them. This, in turn, will cause many problems for our girls in their future life. At present, they are given opportunities like the introduction of 11-year compulsory education in all schools in the country and the creation of conditions for further voluntary education of students in vocational colleges. As taking into account the interests of some of the girls mentioned above, directing them to the profession can effectively help to prevent bad habits among girls. Today, a large number of our young people are using the created conditions wisely and effectively to acquire a profession. They are young people who spend their free time meaningfully as well as materially. It is gratifying that our young girls are among them. But now there are only a few parents who direct our daughters to the profession and take their interests into account. Because they direct their children not to the field they are interested in, but to the profession they want and earn a lot of money, it causes indifference to the profession among young people and a number of other problems. How can a person who does not love his profession become a professional? How does it benefit the people and society? The fact that parents do not allow girls to choose a profession and pursue this profession is damaging girls' interests in the profession. In addition, girls' lack of knowledge about their chosen professions is an obstacle for them to pursue this field. Currently, the untimely issuance of loans for our girls who want to start a business, as a result

of the negligence of some people, leads to the fact that girls do not engage in this profession. In addition, marrying our daughters without any training and education to profession has caused financial difficulties and disagreements in the family. It can also lead to divorce. There is no end to the list of such problems.

Now we need to do the following to solve these problems.

1. Development of a new mechanism for the education and vocational guidance of girls,
2. Establish a strong link between parents, community and educational institutions,
3. Strengthen the role of parents and teachers in educating girls,
4. Organize psychologist meetings with mentally depressed girls.
5. Organize electronic surveys in educational institutions to find out what profession girls want to have and interview parents on the results of surveys
6. Create an electronic "List of Professions" to prevent girls from hesitation in choosing a profession and provide more information about the activities of these chosen professions.
7. Conducting master classes with highly qualified professionals and specialists to help girls become professionals in their field.
8. Organize various professional competitions among girls.

The above-mentioned proposals will lay the foundation for the education of girls and their professional development and help them to overcome the difficulties that arise in their professional activities. Educated, intelligent girls will always have their positions in society and become leading professionals in their field. An enlightened woman is the path to the development of society, because she is the one who raises children and shapes their consciousness, worldview, level of knowledge. An educated woman first and foremost realizes that the wealth of the family is in a healthy and educated generation, investing in education and medicine and making a unique investment in their prosperous future.

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